

Brasilia Facing the Future

Even before 1960, the year of the inauguration of Brasilia, a metropolis started to take shape in the Federal District, having Brasilia as its nucleus, and the satellite-towns and the urban settlements in the adjacent region as its periphery.

Although unwanted by many, this metropolis inexorably developed during the last forty years, following the same patterns of the other Brazilian large cities. The Federal District now has a population of 2,1 million, of which roughly 25% live in the planned area and in its immediate periphery. The remaining 1,55 million are distributed among the satellite towns and other official settlements, not to speak of the innumerable illegal developments that insidiously proliferate throughout the territory.

This large and thinly populated metropolis is believed by many to be the true Brasilia, the real capital city of the country. Center and periphery complement each other and become specialized, revealing, as in other Brazilian large cities, a pronounced social stratification that reflects itself in the flagrant discrepancy between the central area and the most remote urban settlements.

For many years now, both scholars and the general public have acknowledged that this metropolis is best described by the name of "Brasilia". A recent survey, done by a major local newspaper, reveals that, in its great majority, the dwellers of the satellite-towns define themselves as living in Brasilia.

The Brasilia that Lúcio Costa designed in 1956, and that has now been awarded by UNESCO the status of "World Heritage", is now called "Pilot-Plan" by the population, a term that will be adopted in this paper, for simplicity's sake. The people who live in the satellite-towns, when heading to the central areas of the metropolis, often say that they are "going to the Plan", in an involuntarily ironic reference to the fact that they are an "unplanned" population living in "unplanned spaces".

From 1960 to 1996, the urban areas of the Federal District swelled from 25 to 411 square kilometers, which represents an expansion of approximately 1.650%. Considering that the law prescribes that the Government is responsible for the totality of land subdivision within the limits of the Federal District, it was expected that the urban expansion would be carried out in a manner that would reflect a strategy for the occupation of the territory, in conjunction with an economic and social development policy. On the other hand, it would be highly desirable that the different areas created in the course of time would be subjected to a consistent practice of urban design, so that the urban tissue of the city as a whole could become a coherent mosaic of well-articulated and pleasant neighborhoods.

But that has not occurred. The city's administration has lost control over the expansion process of the metropolis that is growing around the Pilot Plan. The "ink-stain" is spreading, mainly in the form of illegal developments, to create a radial city that might eventually blot out the linear design of the Pilot Plan.

However, it is believed that the time and the opportunity still exist for the government to exert, with a stronger determination, its leadership role in the process of ordering the occupation of the territory, and of creating towns/neighborhoods that are both pleasant as living spaces and balanced in terms of the number of residences and jobs.

In this report we will present two projects designed by commission of the Federal District government (GDF): the urbanistic plans for Águas Claras (1993) and the Noroeste Neighborhood (2000). These two cases exemplify peculiar circumstances of the urbanistic activity in Brasília. They are both concerned with the quality of the urban life, but reflect two specific situations, two different contexts: Águas Claras, located in the expansion area outside the Pilot Plan, is mostly committed to enhancing the metropolis urban form, whereas the Noroeste Neighborhood stands as one of the few opportunities of a Pilot Plan's expansion within the "World Heritage" precinct, and it is, therefore, largely committed to the spirit and shape of the capital city created by Lúcio Costa.

Fig. 1 – Federal district map showing the distribution of urban areas and the location of the projects that will be the subject of this report.

Águas Claras

The discontinuous urban occupation of the Federal District imposes a high cost on the quality of life of the city as a whole. The large population concentrations of the Federal District, the two poles that confer on the metropolis its functional configuration, are the complexes Pilot Plan, on one side, and Cruzeiro/Guará and, at a distance of 20 kilometers to the west - Taguatinga/Ceilândia/Samambaia, on the other. In between these two conglomerations, there existed a territorial gap of substantial dimensions, which represented a very serious obstacle to the systems of transportation and to the networks of public services, and also imposed high social costs on the population

Fig. 2 – The once empty area, divided by the Metro tracks, was occupied by the new neighborhood's development to establish a urban continuum.

The authorities in charge of the construction of the Metro (the subway system) perceived the need and the opportunity of occupying that space, the missing link that would ensure urban continuity along the mass transportation system.

The briefing received by the team in charge of that project demanded the creation of "super-blocks" similar to those of the Pilot Plan, to be distributed along the Metro lines, which, at that moment, had already been defined as the structuring elements of the new neighborhood.

The said team, together with the technical staff of the GDF, as a first step, proceeded to work on a deeper formulation of the rationale of the plan. From the very start, it was established that the new urban area would not be another dormitory-neighborhood, but a dynamic metropolitan pole, shaped by the economic, social and cultural forces, so as to house, besides residential areas, spaces intended for other urban activities such as commerce, services, leisure, administration, etc., creating an attractive pole for the various regions of the metropolis and functioning as a powerful job-generator.

Besides, the plan should contemplate the conservation of nature and of the landscape, of great scenic beauty and notable for its valleys, slopes and ciliary woods.

The team responsible for the project intended to start both from an objective evaluation of the voca-

tion of the site, and from a conceptual formulation based on a thirty-year long experience, both professional and academic, in the most part dedicated to Brasília, the largest and most expressive expression of modernistic urbanism in the whole world. The urbanistic directives to be adopted were subjected to deep consideration, so as to avoid the thoughtless repetition of the solutions that characterize that great and time honored "model". Giving full attention to the critic of the modernistic urban design, and thoroughly committed to the "doing now", we set out a reasonably coherent framework for working out the plan.

Fig. 3 – General Perspective

At the bottom of the figure shown above we can see part of the central area of Taguatinga, and, on the horizon, the outline of the Pilot Plan, surrounded by the Paranoá Lake. The new neighborhood is located on an empty area four kilometers long, measuring 808 hectares, 460 of which will be occupied by the urban grid.

A Metro junction marks the core of the new neighborhood. The sinuosity of the Metro lines creates a certain degree of formal intrigue, that has set us free from the monotony of an orthogonal road network, fragmenting the urban landscape into segments that propitiate the creation of the desired gregarious scale.

Two large avenues, Araucária and Castanheira, running parallel to the Metro lines, form a binary that defines the urban road network. Running along the total urban extension, these two avenues delimit two distinct urban tissues: the super-blocks, that were distributed along the strips on the outer side of the binary, and the conventional blocks, that form a denser urban tissue, more similar to that of traditional cities, located on its inner side, running along the metro lines. A transversal system of streets structure these blocks, that are intended for residential, institutional, and commercial uses.

The plan intended to duplicate certain solutions that are typical of the Pilot Plan, and that have proved positive, such as the super-block; and special attention was given to the creation of pleasant and harmonious spaces intended for community life. To

Fig. 4 – The traditional blocks along the Metro line, the super-blocks in the outside strip; the boulevards reach the stations; bridges for vehicles and pedestrians ensure the integration of the Neighborhood's parts.

that end, arcades, pedestrian streets and squares were designed, forming a system of public spaces in which the population can circulate and meet in conditions of safety and tranquility, without an excess of conflict with the motorized traffic.

In this network of avenues and streets, the pedestrian is given preference. Traffic lights, pedestrian strips and bridges that cross over the Metro lines guarantee their safety and their mobility, thus checking the dominance of the motor vehicles.

Most of the Metro lines are set in trenches, allowing several roads to cross over the tracks, thus providing the necessary communication between the two main avenues. Running along the Metro trenches, a tree lined boulevard giving access to the adjoining buildings was created, allowing the population to reach the stations along shaded paths.

Fig. 5 – The friendly relationship between the Metro, beneath road level, and the boulevards with its buildings.

The activities of commerce, services and leisure will be located next to the Metro stations, both in the central area, around the Águas Claras Station, and in the secondary centers, together with schools, health-care centers and hospitals, thus forming highly dynamic urban spaces. To sum up, the intention is to vitalize the central areas and, simultaneously, to establish a mixed zoning, where different urban activities will share the same space.

Another directive adopted concerned the addition of other ingredients, aiming at enhancing the neigh-

borhood. What was being proposed was the retrieval of a repertoire that is familiar to many Brazilian towns: a privileged network of meeting-places, characterized by an intense and diversified use of the space, is distributed along squares, broad sidewalks, busy street corners, and well-defined avenues and streets.

The aim is to afford freedom of choice, offering the population the broadest range of alternatives possible in choosing locations for residences, commerce, services and leisure activities. A certain degree of zoning will be present, however, in order to provide spaces that are adequate for the different activities. It will be a flexible zoning, however, one that will not prevent the initial plan from gradually adapting to the evolution of society. The formula adopted for the creation of a pleasant town and an agreeable neighborhood was, therefore, the establishment of esthetical, social and functional rules, which, however, should be flexible enough to be adapted to the purposes of the community, as they change in the course of time.

Such was the idea that lay behind the design of this neighborhood- town: a town with 460 hectares of urban areas, for a population around 160.000, with a gross density of 350 inhabitants per hectare. A dense and dynamic town, that should contain both the energy of a metropolitan center and the colloquial scale of the residential areas.

Also rediscussed was the issue of public spaces and green areas. Avoiding the temptation of scattering the buildings along extensive public parks, it was understood that this quasi-rural type of structure does not meet important expectations related to the desired urban character of the neighborhood. Urban vitality, associated with ideas of continuity, contiguity, density and coziness, calls for the right selection and the right arrangement of the repertoire of public spaces and green areas, which should bring together, rather than separate the buildings.

The main green area within the urban fabric is the Águas Claras Urban Park, located in the central area, next to the integration station of the Metro lines. Measuring around twelve hectares, it presents a varied topography, with high promontories and spots of remarkable scenic value. Also, located within walking distance of all the residential areas, is a large Metropolitan Park, with approximately 63 hectares, and associated to the main Unit of Conservation existing within the site, the *Granja Águas Claras*, the official residence of the Governor, which, in the near future, may become an area open to the public.

Also, next to the blocks, 26 public squares will be constructed, adding 9,6 hectares of green areas and leisure facilities which permeate the urban area. Within each of the super-blocks a well-defined square was created for the use of the resident population. These

squares are not the residual product of the geometric exercise of distributing blocks and buildings, but were intentionally located and designed as community assets, to be used and cherished by the population.

In regard to the urban infrastructure, water supply has been treated as the fundamental issue for the development of the Federal District. The resolution of the sanitary problem involves policies of conservation and recovery of the environment, as shall be seen ahead.

Noroeste Neighborhood

In the case of the urban plan for the Águas Claras Neighborhood, our work has developed from an objective examination of the site and the Neighborhood's vocations, with a certain amount of freedom to look for solutions committed to "urbanity". In the case of the Noroeste Neighborhood, however, the project's rationale was already established.

Lúcio Costa, in his document "Brasília Revisited" pondered: "Once the protection of that which is to be preserved is ensured, one must now verify where the occupation – mostly residential – can be convenient in areas close to the Pilot Plan, that is to say, in the Paranoá Basin, and how this occupation should be conducted in order to integrate into that which already exists, in shape and spirit, ratifying the characterization of the park city – "sprawling and concise" - suggested as the differentiating urban outline of the capital." (Costa, 1987)

The project for the new neighborhood was born with a pre-established genetic map. The Pilot Plan's super-blocks stand as a necessary reference, not only because of the recommendations included in the document, but also because they already belong to the collective imagery of the local society.

Nevertheless, the urban plan for the Noroeste Neighborhood was conducted on the basis of some reflections on the urbanistic experience of the Pilot Plan; on successes, deviations, surprises and improvisations, which have left some lessons, surely of great value to future urban projects.

It's important to point out that the protection of Brasília's architectural and urban heritage does not imply an attitude of reproduction and copy of what has been done in the past. For the sake of respect for a work that should be admired and defended, the risk of mechanical or simplistic reproduction of its original conception should be precluded, for it would demerit rather than praise the plan of this World Heritage Site.

Urban Structure

The Neighborhood's urbanistic proposal is based on a quadrangular road grid that defines cells of approximately 500 x 500 meters, which in turn, constitute large Residential Units by means of the clustering of four super-blocks, with 250 x 250 meters each,

resembling the ones present in the Pilot Plan. The expectation was that these clusters, would expand the areas of the pedestrian domain, thus emphasizing the pleasant sensation of living in a park.

These Residential Units are adjacent to the North Ecological Park, whose master plan has been revised. The characteristics of the park city, already consolidated in the super-block concept, will thus be enhanced.

All super blocks, specially those ten bordering the avenue that delimitates the park, will enjoy a privileged situation. Their dwellers will need to walk no more than 500 meters to reach their recreational, sports and cultural leisure areas. The Park presents itself as an important environmental unit, inserted between the urban networks of the North Wing and the new Neighborhood

Fig. 6 – The Neighborhood touches the park, next to which, twenty super-blocks form the long residential sector. Another narrower strip will house other activities of community interest.

Parallel to the rank of residential blocks, a long strip, 150 meters wide, houses other activities of interest to the inhabitants of the Neighborhood and its region of influence: hospitals, health-care centers, schools, neighborhood clubs, supermarkets, movie theaters, sport yards etc. Basically, these are activities that are now present in the large areas that are now present in the large areas between the super blocks of the Pilot Plan.

The point here is that the neighborhood and its facilities should not be organized merely to configure vicinal spaces.

Fig. 7 – Three elements from the proposal: the cluster of four super-blocks, the binary of the local commerce and the longitudinal strip of community facilities.

In the case of the Pilot Plan, Lúcio Costa distributed blocks and facilities in an open and non-restrictive manner. The city Plan, wisely took into account the fact that the social relationships of a city the size of Brasília do not present an essentially parochial feature. The community needs open public places for aggregation and social contact.

The Neighborhood, although having its own identity and character, will enable the constitution of an open community, integrated into the total city. A consequence of this acknowledgment is that the facilities were located in such way that they will serve both the community residents and an outside public, comprising the inhabitants of the immediate neighborhood (North Wing) and the ones living in more remote areas of the city.

Local Commerce

Toward the east-west direction, the large residential units are divided by local commerce strips, served by a binary of one-way roads that will also give access to the super-blocks. Local commerce will be organized in buildings similar to those in the North Wing, on 26 x 26 m plots aligned inside the binary.

In this new proposal for the local commerce, the roads that form the binary are constituted on one side by the commercial blocks and on the other by the super-block social facilities: preschool, primary school, leisure areas and restaurants for the neighborhood unities, arranged along a sidewalk shadowed by the green belt that surrounds each super-block

That's the place for florist shops, newsstands and specially designed kiosks to accommodate locksmiths, dressmakers, shoemakers, plumbers, electricians and so on.

In this way, we tried to overcome the front/rear dichotomy that has been affecting current solutions for the local commerce, both in North and South Wing

Fig. 8 – On one side, the sidewalk with the super-block's social facilities, on the other, the buildings with commerce and services.

The commercial activities will be accommodated in three-story buildings (a shop with a mezzanine and two more pavements). Underground parking garages should be provided for the dwellers, store

owners and employees. This pattern was also applied to the buildings intended for activities related to security (police post or police station), health and worship. Buildings destined to worship will be allowed to have towers and other elements of symbolic and expressive character.

Road Network

We chose to direct the Neighborhood's main traffic system toward the central area of the city, more specifically toward the Monumental Axis, to where the main circulation corridors will be channeled, offering interesting views of its main landmarks, such as the TV Tower and the Sports Gymnasium.

Fig. 9 – Structural, distribution and local roads and the Park's private tracks define the road network of the ensemble, oriented toward the Monumental Axis, parallel to the North Wing.

The road network was structured by means of three north-south avenues: the avenue that delimitates the park and the two avenues that form the binary serving the blocks along the longitudinal strip.

Instead of major road interventions, the plan points to solutions that contribute to the neighborhood's "urbanity", causing minimum environmental impact. The land uses on the strips lining the avenues should be compatible with their features and the intensity of traffic they can hold.

Pedestrian circulation was privileged in the traffic system design. As in Águas Claras, well-defined paths, traffic lights, crosswalks and passages in different levels are included in the repertoire of design solutions for the public space.

Neighborhood Population

With an estimate of 1.800 inhabitants per super-block, the twenty projected super-blocks will accommodate approximately 36.000 dwellers. Adding to this number approximately 3.800 more dwellers, who will live in the commercial and service areas, the estimated population for the future Neighborhood is 40.000 inhabitants. Assuming that the neighborhood was designed for a middle class population with characteristics similar to that of the Pilot Plan, the community facilities, the commercial and service areas will be similarly mixed and dimensioned.

Park Master Plan

An important feature of both projects is the association of the urbanistic plans to the adjacent parks. In the case of the Noroeste Neighborhood, an expressive expansion of an existing park, the Burle Marx Park, was proposed, thus rendering it more visible to the city. Based on a second reading of vocations and on the consequent revision of goals, the new design and zoning expanded the park area from 175 to 300 hectares.

Discarding its present sad role, hidden behind backyards, the park will be an expressive part of the Pilot Plan landscape. A visual and functional continuity with the existing southern park, "Parque da Cidade", will be then achieved, provided that a new landscape treatment for the surroundings of the Racetrack and the Sports Sector is undertaken.

The relationship between the Park and the existing and planned activities in its immediate surroundings, the need to preserve the remaining native vegetation and to promote the recovery of degraded areas, together with the natural relief conformations, provided the specific conditions for the establishment of a new zoning. Five large zones were defined:

- Zone 1 - Sports and cultural activities
- Zone 2 - Seedling production and environmental recovery
- Zone 3 - Administration
- Zone 4 - Recreational, scientific and educational activities
- Zone 5 - Preservation

The Neighborhood's Infrastructure

Concerning infrastructure, the major principle is that cities, like any other human activity, should pursue maximum sustainability and harmony with the environment. Therefore, full advantage should be taken of any opportunity to recover and maintain natural resources, such as the Paranoá basin, whose vulnerability has been acknowledged since the first studies aiming at the construction of the capital.

Fig. 10 – After the expansion of the Park limits and the updating of its activities, a new zoning was produced, respecting the project selected in a public competition. The axis toward the Television Tower organizes the distribution of landmarks and sites.

The simultaneous implementation of the Burle Marx Park and the Noroeste Neighborhood presents a unique opportunity to engender innumerable solutions for the hydrological resources preservation, both through the reuse of the water from the Paranoá Lake and through the recycling of used water. Nevertheless, the alternatives to sanitation should be conceived in sintony with the water supply and sanitation agencies.

In accordance with the educational function of Burle Marx Park, it's not advisable to use potable water in irrigation, formation or maintenance of the ponds proposed in its land use plan.

This directive strengthens the "ecological" feature of the Park, revealing to the users a more practical and effective side of the quest for the sustainable use of natural resources. The water for those purposes should be obtained from the Paranoá Lake, captured at any point between the mouth of the Bananal stream and the North Wing Sewage Treatment Plant. The water pumped from the Paranoá Lake should be cast into the first pond, which will act as a polishing tank. From this reservoir, it will be directed to other uses, including other projected ponds and fountains.

Finally, I wish to point out that we have, throughout these studies, clearly privileged "urbanity", therefore the two proposals share the quality of providing people with the unique opportunity of living "the magic of the town"; cities and parks should be associated without losing their integrity and their peculiarities. Their nature should be acknowledged and respected. Furthermore, both solutions are devoted to the protection and appreciation of the environment, taking into consideration the fragilities of the site's hydrographic system.

REFERENCES

These plans were drawn up by commission of the officials and technicians of the Federal District Government, through the Secretary of Urban Development and Housing – SEDUH and the Secretary of Environment and Hydrological Resources - SEMARH.

Collaboration: SINDUSCON, ASBRACO and ADEMI.
Technical Services produced by Zimbres Arquitetos Associados

Technical Team

Urbanism: Architects Paulo Zimbres, Geraldo Sá Nogueira Batista, Luiz Antonio Reis, Otto Ribas and José Renato Carvalho

Environment and Sanitation: Otto Ribas and Eng. José de Sena Pereira Jr.

Landscape design: Eurico João Salviatti

Technical Coordination: Arch. Marcos Zimbres

Production Coordination: Arch. Joara Cronemberger

Production Team: Architects Mônica Schramm and

Cláudia Sobreira

Perspectives: Architect Luiz Antonio Vallandro Keating

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Paulo Zimbres. Architect, was born in Ouro Preto, in 1933. A graduate from the FAU-USP (São Paulo, 1960). Master of Philosophy (M. Phil. in Urban Design - University of Edinburgh (1974). Private practice in São Paulo (1961-1968). Professor-Adjunct at the University of Brasília (1968-1991); Chief of the Architecture and Urbanism Department (1975-1977). President of CODEPLAN-GDF (1989-1990). Private practice in Brasília - Senior Architect in Zimbres Arquitetos Associados. Awarded the *Grande Prêmio Ex-Aequo* in the general exhibition of architects in the Fourth Architecture Biennial of São Paulo (1999) for the *Unimep Theater* (1998).